

Early Warning System for PCOS

Sathvik Kurapati

Student, Redmond, Washington, USA

<https://sites.google.com/view/sathvikkurapati/home>

email: sathvik.kurapati2020@gmail.com

Keerthana Kurapati

Student, Redmond, Washington, USA

email: rachelkurapati2020@gmail.com

Mentor: Vrushali Gersappe

Psychiatrist, Swedish, Redmond, Washington, USA

email: vgersappe@gmail.com

Abstract— Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) is a hormonal disorder affecting 6- 26% of women in the reproductive age group worldwide [*1]. Diagnosing Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) in adolescents can be very difficult. Symptoms of PCOS such as acne, weight gain, and irregular periods can often be confused with signs of normal puberty. Due to the lack of awareness, education, and taboo around the subject of menstrual cycles, often, girls do not discuss irregular or missed periods with their family members or their peers. Usually, rapid weight gain around puberty, excessive acne, and unwanted hair on arms, legs, and face can cause distress in this age group causing mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, and eating disorders to worsen. Early recognition and detection of “at risk” PCOS cases in adolescent girls can prevent complications such as obesity, insulin resistance, diabetes, infertility, and cardiovascular issues later in life. This paper explores a method to track early indicators like BMI, period health, skin health and weight patterns, detects negative patterns and notifies the user early, before they manifest as PCOS - this helps the user/physician address these issues early on and prevent the user from developing PCOS. The data from the customer validation done suggests a staggering 86.2% success rate of detecting PCOS months/years before they become severe enough to be clinically diagnosed as PCOS.

Keywords— Women and Health, Healthcare, e-healthcare, AI, Analytics, COVID-19, Emotions, Stress, Physical factors, Periods, Menstrual Irregularity

I. Introduction

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a hormonal disorder affecting 6-26% of women in the reproductive age group worldwide [*1]. This is a condition where there is an excess of androgen (male hormone) being secreted by the ovaries leading to irregular, missed, or heavy periods, weight gain, and acne. Hirsutism (male-pattern hair growth or unwanted hair on face, arms, back and legs) is also a common feature. PCOS also causes metabolic syndrome leading to weight gain, insulin resistance, and high cholesterol increasing cardiovascular risk. PCOS increases the risk of infertility, and it is commonly diagnosed when conception becomes difficult.

As per CDC, PCOS can be diagnosed during adolescent years, however, most cases of PCOS come to light in their 20s or 30s, around their reproductive era while struggling with infertility. The condition can be treated much more effectively when detected makes but the lack of explicit symptoms make early detection very difficult.

The advancement of technology and prevalence of smart phones allow us to simplify the problem and alert the user sooner to effectively help the patient. This paper explores a mechanism that could act as an early indicator of PCOS in teens and can be used by teens, pediatricians, and parents to offer timely help.

II. PROBLEM DESCRIPTION

A. Problem Definition

Polycystic ovarian syndrome is one of the common endocrine disorders in teens - a disorder that causes cysts to develop on the ovaries. Due to wide range of symptoms, different diagnostic criteria and lack of awareness of the disease itself, 50-75% of women with PCOS are not aware that they have it [*2]. As per CDC, 6-12% of women have PCOS and 5 million of childbearing age women are affected by this condition. PCOS can occur any time after puberty, however, most people get diagnosed only in their 20s or 30s.

Due to the general lack of awareness, education, and taboo around the subject of menstrual cycles, often, girls do not discuss irregular or missed periods with their family members or their peers. This can lead to minimizing symptoms such as missed periods or concealment undesirable hair on back, arms, legs, and face. This can also lead to subconsciously adopting a forgetful mindset and lacking awareness of irregular or heavy periods and failing to bring this up with their healthcare providers during routine pediatric visits. Internal turmoil and distress in this age group can lead to worsening of mental health issues such as anxiety, depression, struggles with low self-esteem, social isolation and eating disorders to worsen in adolescents.

Signs and symptoms of PCOS can start in adolescent girls (AFAB) and often confused with puberty. Lack of awareness and education regarding PCOS can lead to increased risk of infertility, obesity, diabetes, cardiovascular disease, and endometrial cancer in later years.

B. Diagnosis

Often, the diagnosis of PCOS in adolescents differed for 2 years after giving consideration to the fact that some of the symptoms overlap with natural puberty transitions. Also, the international evidence-based guidelines clearly state that the general methods for diagnosing adult PCOS cannot be applied to adolescent girls.

There are 3 main criteria for diagnosing PCOS.

I. Hyperandrogenism- is considered to be a hallmark of PCOS. It is a condition where there is dominance of male hormone, androgen secreted abnormally by the ovaries leading to hirsutism (male-pattern hair growth or unwanted hair growth on face, arms, back and legs), acne, excessive weight gain and other biological male characteristics (virilization).

II. Anovulation, chronic- where ovaries fail to release eggs leading to irregular periods or absence of periods and may also lead to heavy bleeding due to hormonal imbalance.

III. Polycystic ovaries- cysts on ovaries as seen on ultrasound.

Diagnostic tools such as Rotterdam criteria or the Androgen Excess Society criteria cannot be applied to adolescent girls and the diagnosis of PCOS is differed for at least 2 years as symptoms of PCOS such as acne, weight gain, and irregular periods can overlap with puberty transitions making early detection difficult.

A. Treatment options

The first line of treatment for PCOS is often considered to be lifestyle modifications such as dietary adjustments, exercising on regular basis, and working on stress reduction. There are studies showing 5-7% of weight reduction can restore regular menstrual periods and reduction in the risk of developing insulin resistance and diabetes and thereby reducing the cardiovascular complications. Early recognition and detection of “at risk” cases of PCOS in adolescent girls can prevent complications such as obesity, insulin resistance, diabetes, infertility, and cardiovascular complications later in life. Birth control pills for period regulation as well as starting metformin early on for insulin resistance can help alleviate signs/symptoms of PCOS.

B. Why current methods are ineffective

Early detection of these symptoms leading to adopting a healthier lifestyle, including better nutrition, regular exercise, and stress management, can greatly benefit the health of adolescent girls. PCOS can be very difficult to diagnose during adolescence and puberty in AFAB (assigned female at birth) as symptoms such as acne, weight gain, missed periods can be confused as signs/symptoms of puberty and often the diagnosis of PCOS is differed for 2 years in adolescent girls. There are currently no set diagnostic screening tools or early detection tools available in capturing data such as weight gain and missed periods in adolescent AFAB (age 13-21).

IV. Hypothesis

There is a clear indication from literature that multiple symptoms show up as early indicators which can eventually lead to PCOS.

1. Rapid weight gain
2. Missing/Irregular periods
3. Skin Discoloration/Excessive Acne
4. Excessive Hair growth

One problem that is keeping PCOS from being diagnosed and treated early on is the fact that the main symptoms of the disease are those that come along with puberty, and therefore most women and even healthcare providers dismiss them as a natural phenomenon without thinking to investigate. Since PCOS is usually diagnosed by looking for a combination

of these factors, most adolescent girls are not tracking or taking into account these factors because of a lack of awareness, making it harder to diagnose. Although the app is not meant for diagnosing PCOS, it will be able to make predictions based on trends in data and surface the problem to the woman, who can then tell a physician. Early detection by monitoring this data, can help doctors and patients address problems before they become severe, avoiding potential complications.

The following table aids as a tool to untangle the indicators and clearly tie them to either Natural Puberty or PCOS.

	Natural Puberty	PCOS
Missing periods	Irregular periods since start of menarche (1st period).	Cycles longer than 45 days, 2 years after the onset of the first period suggests that PCOS should be investigated. Also, never had first period or, irregular, heavy cycles shorter than 21 days or bleeding for >7 days in a row.
Weight gain in correlation to height	Weight/Height ratio BMI remains steady	Increase in weight/ BMI
Hair Growth	Hair growth around arm pits and public region	Thicker hair growth on face, upper lip, chin, arms, back and legs
Acne	Small acne around nose, forehead, cheeks. Routine skin care helps resolve this problem	Excessive acne, red and cyst like, on jawline, chin, neck, cheeks. Does not respond to topical acne treatments
Skin discoloration (neck, joint folds) Acanthosis Nigricans	Not present	Commonly associated darkening of skin around neck, armpits, and groin.

This subtle but quantified difference will help associate the severity of the symptoms to PCOS thereby allowing us to read a clear signal. This step is crucial in determining the early onset of PCOS which can inform the user early on and seek help in timely manner from their healthcare providers.

How do we detect anomalies?

Based on the studies from literature, given enough data points, statistical correlation can be drawn to classify the changes in each of these values. This classification aids detection of anomalies in the readings and helps call them out objectively.

	Natural Puberty	PCOS
Weight gain in correlation to height	BMI remains steady	Increase in BMI (more than 10% of body weight gain)
Missing periods	Irregular periods are common in first 2 years after start of menarche	Beyond 2 years of start of periods, cycles >45 days, or heavy cycles shorter than 21 days with bleeding lasting for 7 days.
Skin discoloration	None	Darkening of skin around neck, armpits, and groin
Acne Hair growth	Acne- resolve with good skin care routine, Hair mostly in armpits and pubic region needing frequent shaving	Excessive, dark hair growth on face, upper lip, chin, arms, legs, back causing distress and requiring frequent shaving

V. Customer Validation

We did a survey of around 248 women and 14.1% of them said that they have been diagnosed with PCOS.

Below is the statistics from users that are not diagnosed with PCOS.

Below are the stats from users that are diagnosed with PCOS.

If you were diagnosed with PCOS,

At what age were you diagnosed with PCOS?

Copy

35 responses

Did you experience any of the following signs/symptoms in your teenage years upon starting menstrual cycles: (select all that apply)

Copy

35 responses

Analysis of the data from the survey indicates that the algorithm we have detects a staggering 86.2% of PCOS cases well (years) before they are diagnosable as PCOS. This can play a significant role in helping treat them early when they are minor complications and help prevent the user from developing PCOS. Below is a chart that shows the same for a reduced sample size.

After comparing the conclusion by the app vs the real fact reported by the user, flagging one or more conditions as a concern and alerting the user early helped us catch 24 out of 29 PCOS cases in a sample size of 120 population. Among the people that app said has PCOS, 86.2% of them actually ended up having it.

There were false positives as shown by the orange bar above which denotes the users that are notified by the app but did not actually ended up having PCOS. These false positives are not a huge concern as they usually indicate of other health issues if not PCOS – and helping the user stay on top of their overall health.

VI. Proposed Model

The widespread availability of smartphones, health apps, and wearables has made it easier than ever to track health data, both automatically and manually. Leveraging smartphone technology allows us to capture and collect a good sample of data over a period of time.

This paper introduces “Amber” an app that helps teenage girls to stay ahead and prevent PCOS. The proposal is to track menstrual cycles, weight, height, and stress levels, and provide notifications that encourage adolescent girls to seek medical and counseling help early on. By starting lifestyle changes such as weight management, stress reduction, and good sleep habits, they can prevent serious health complications later in life. Girls between the ages of 13-21 can use the app Amber, to track these parameters – periods, weight, and activity level (exercise, healthy eating habits, sleep, and stress levels) on regular basis. The app can use this data and detect any anomalies and notify the user to contact their physician. For example, the app can flag any abnormal increase in weight or irregular periods and alert these changes to the user that sometimes can go unnoticed.

Following criteria can be used to flag a concern for PCOS:

- BMI increase > 10% (based on historical studies on girls of this age group)
- Missed or irregular periods for more than 3-6 turns after onset of puberty, distress due to excessive hair growth on face, arms, legs and acanthosis nigricans (discoloration of skin on neck, armpits, other joint creases indicative of insulin resistance)

The value of this app would be twofold.

1. It would allow for predicting whether someone is at risk of PCOS based on the past data that they have logged. Linear extrapolation will be used (i.e. the data will be plotted on a linear graph with the x-axis showing time and the y-axis showing the measured values. If the slope of the calculated linear trendline is positive, then that means that there is a potential chance for an increase in weight gain) and will therefore allow one to know if they are at risk for PCOS.
2. Another valuable feature of this app is that it would allow one to see how severe their situation is based on the current data that they have entered. As the app keeps track of these pieces of data longer than a girl tends to, it has an advantage because it can use the data to bring awareness to the girl and her healthcare provider while also classifying severity based on a combination of the issues. It can also help to bring awareness to the issue and allow girls to take steps to counteract it early on.

The app includes a variety of educational resources to increase the user's knowledge and understanding of important health metrics. These resources could be anything from tracking their steps, diet to encouraging the user to improve sleep and reduce stress through meditation and other hobbies. By tracking and collecting data, it allows the user to monitor the improvement in these parameters as they make lifestyle changes. This historical data tracking can help surface these as graphs and motivate/educate the user to maintain their healthy habits. The alerting system based on the current trends and predictions and educating the user to stay ahead of any issues leading to PCOS can greatly help and prevent PCOS.

Data Schema:

There are two tables that we use to store the data pertaining to the user.

1. **UserProfile** table: holds the data about the user like nick name, age, date of onset of periods etc. This data is static and is recorded one time and can be updated at any given time by going to the profile update page. The update experience is trivial and excluded from the paper for brevity.
2. **UserPCOSData** table: holds data about the various parameters pertaining to users health which are relevant to PCOS risk computation

For every parameter there are two factors:

1. How bad is the parameter on the regular health chart. Example: the person did not gain weight last month but in general the weight of the person is 300 pounds which is generally unhealthy
2. How bad is the delta compared to last month. Example: the person gained 10 pounds in the last month which is unhealthy

Below is how the schema of the **UserProfile** table looks like:

Field	Data Type	Description
Name	Varchar(200)	Name of the user
DOB	DateTime	Date of birth of the user
PeriodOnsetDate	DateTime	Month/year of onset of periods

Below is how the schema of the **UserPCOSData** table looks like:

Field	Data Type	Description
Date	Datetime	Date of the event/data
Height	Integer	Height of the user
Weight	Integer	Weight of the user
HasIrregularPeriod	Boolean	Indicates if there are period irregularities
IrregularPeriodIntensity	Integer	A number between 1 to 10 where 1 is normal and 10 is severely bad
HasSkinIssue	Boolean	Indicates if there are skin issues
SkinIssueIntensity	Integer	A number between 1 to 10 where 1 is normal and 10 is severely bad
HasHairIssue	Boolean	Indicates if there are hair issues
HairIssueIntensity	Integer	A number between 1 to 10 where 1 is normal and 10 is severely bad

For example, below could be the contents of the **UserPCOSData** table for *Sarah* at a given point in time.

Date	Height	Weight	HasIrregularPeriod	IrregularPeriodIntensity	HasSkinIssue	SkinIssueIntensity	HasHairIssue	HairIssueIntensity
11/10/2022	5.8	130	Y	8	N	1	N	1
12/10/2022	5.8	130	Y	7	N	1	Y	2
1/10/2023	5.8	135	Y	7	Y	2	Y	2

The app would track data about the following parameters through automated and manual mechanisms:

```

    /// <summary>
    /// Represents if the user has irregular periods
    /// </summary>
    int hasIrregularPeriod;

    /// <summary>
    /// Represents the severity of the period problems
    /// </summary>
    int irregularPeriodIntensity;

    /// <summary>
    /// Represents if the user has skin issues
    /// </summary>
    int hasSkinIssue;

    /// <summary>
    /// Represents the severity of the skin problems
    /// </summary>
    int skinIssueIntensity;

    /// <summary>
    /// Represents if the user has hair issues
    /// </summary>
    int hasHairIssue;

    /// <summary>
    /// Represents the severity of the hair problems
    /// </summary>
    int hairIssueIntensity;

```

The following are the conditions:

1. BMI Calculation: We calculate two values for BMI 1. bmiFlag and 2. bmiIntensity. bmiFlag indicates if the recent change in bmi is a concern and bmiIntensity indicates if the current bmi of the user is a concern.

We will flag the rate of BMI change as an issue if there is more than 10% of body weight gain in the last 3 months.

Let's say that the h1, w1 is the minimum height and weight of the user in the last 3 months; and the height and weight this month is h2 and w2.

```

/// <summary>
/// Computes the BMI state and returns if it is healthy or not
/// </summary>
/// <param name="w1">Minimum weight of the user in the last 3 months</param>
/// <param name="h1">Minimum height of the user in the last 3 months</param>
/// <param name="w2">Current weight of the user</param>
/// <param name="h2">Current height of the user</param>
/// <returns>>true if the bmi change is concerning else it returns false</returns>
bool IsBMIChangeConcerning(int w1, int h1, int w2, int h2)
{
    int bmi1, bmi2;
    bool bmiFlag = false;
    bmi1 = w1 / h1;
    bmi2 = w2 / h2;
    if ((bmi2 - bmi1) = 0.1 * bmi1)
    {
        bmiFlag = true;
    }

    return bmiFlag;
}

```

We can also calculate how bad the users BMI is on the general BMI chart and rank the BMI Intensity for the user from 1-10; lets call that rank as bmiIntensity.

```

/// <summary>
/// A function to find if the bmi of a user is in the healthy range or not
/// </summary>
/// <returns>>true if the bmi is in unhealthy range, else it returns false</returns>
bool IsBMIRankConcerning()
{
    int rank = GetBMIRank();
    if (rank < 5)
        return false;

    return true;
}

/// <summary>
/// Determines the bmi rank
/// </summary>
/// <returns>bmi rank</returns>
int GetBMIRank()
{
    int bmiRank = 0;
    // TO be implemented
    return bmiRank;
}

```

2. Periods health calculation: We calculate two values for periods health 1. periodFlag and 2. periodIssueIntensity. periodFlag indicates if the recent change in period pattern is a concern and periodIssueIntensity indicates if the current irregularity or intensity of periods is a concern.

The data points to if the user is having irregular periods and their intensity is input by the user. The user is specifically prompted to say yes or no the following questions:

- Are you having irregular periods?
- Are your period cycles longer than 45 days?
- Are you having heavy cycles shorter than 21 days with bleeding lasting for 7 days?

A “yes” to any of the above will imply setting the HasIrregularPeriod to true in the UserPCOSData table.

The following functions are used in the calculation of periods health:

```
/// <summary>
/// Returns if the change in periods pattern is concerning
/// </summary>
/// <returns>true if the the period change pattern is concerning else it returns false</returns>
bool IsPeriodChangeConcerning()
{
    return hasIrregularPeriod;
}

/// <summary>
/// A function to find if the user is ingeneral having bad periods
/// </summary>
/// <returns>true if the periods are in the unhealthy range, else it returns false</returns>
bool IsPeriodRankConcerning()
{
    int rank = irregularPeriodIntensity;
    if (rank < 5)
        return false;

    return true;
}
```

3. Skin health calculation: We calculate two values for skin health 1. skinFlag and 2. skinIssueIntensity. skinFlag indicates if the recent change in skin pattern is a concern and skinIssueIntensity indicates if the current state of the skin is a concern i.e. darkening of skin around neck, armpits, and groin etc.

The data points to if the user is having skin issues is input by the user. The user is specifically prompted to say yes or no the following questions:

- Do you have any skin issues from the past - darkening of skin around neck, armpits, and groin?
- Are there recent changes in your skin recent monthly - darkening of skin around neck, armpits, and groin?

```
/// <summary>
/// Returns if the change in skin pattern is concerning
/// </summary>
/// <returns>true if the the skin change pattern is concerning else it returns false</returns>
bool IsSkinChangeConcerning()
{
    return hasSkinIssue;
}

/// <summary>
/// A function to find if the user is ingeneral having bad skin changes
/// </summary>
/// <returns>true if the skin changes are in the unhealthy range, else it returns false</returns>
bool IsSkinRankConcerning()
{
    int rank = skinIssueIntensity;
    if (rank < 5)
        return false;

    return true;
}
```

4. Hair health calculation: We calculate two values for hair health 1. hairFlag and 2. hairIssueIntensity. hairFlag indicates if the recent change in hair pattern is a concern and hairIssueIntensity indicates if the current state of the

hair is a concern i.e. excessive, dark hair growth on face, upper lip, chin, arms, legs, back causing distress and requiring frequent shaving etc.

The data points to if the user is having hair issues is input by the user. The user is specifically prompted to say yes or no the following questions:

- Do you have any hair issues from the past - excessive, dark hair growth on face, upper lip, chin, arms, legs, back causing distress and requiring frequent shaving?
- Are there recent changes in your skin recent monthly - excessive, dark hair growth on face, upper lip, chin, arms, legs, back causing distress and requiring frequent shaving?

```

    /// <summary>
    /// Returns if the change in hair pattern is concerning
    /// </summary>
    /// <returns>true if the the hair change pattern is concerning else it returns false</returns>
    bool IsHairChangeConcerning()
    {
        return hasHairIssue;
    }

    /// <summary>
    /// A function to find if the user is ingeneral having bad hair changes
    /// </summary>
    /// <returns>true if the hair changes are in the unhealthy range, else it returns false</returns>
    bool IsHairRankConcerning()
    {
        int rank = hairIssueIntensity;
        if (rank < 5)
            return false;

        return true;
    }

```

The above functions can be used to determine if the health state of the user (periods or skin or hair) is concerning and if the user should be notified or not.

```
    /// <summary>
    /// Determines if period health is a concern
    /// </summary>
    /// <returns>returns true if period health is concerning</returns>
    bool RaisePeriodsNotification()
    {
        return IsPeriodChangeConcerning() || IsHairRankConcerning();
    }

    /// <summary>
    /// Determines if skin health is a concern
    /// </summary>
    /// <returns>returns true if skin health is concerning</returns>
    bool RaiseSkinNotification()
    {
        return IsSkinChangeConcerning() || IsSkinRankConcerning();
    }

    /// <summary>
    /// Determines if hair health is a concern
    /// </summary>
    /// <returns>returns true if hair health is concerning</returns>
    bool RaiseHairNotification()
    {
        return IsHairChangeConcerning() || IsHairRankConcerning();
    }
}
```

Architecture

The app can integrate with API present on smartphones to fetch the data from the health apps which are already running on the smart phones. For example, Apple iPhones come with integrated health app that exposes API to get the health data that it tracks. The app can also use manual methods like periodic surveys and polls to ask the user to quickly fill in or select data points that will inform the app. These datapoints are stored in a local data store for further processing.

The following architecture diagram depicts some of the components and their interaction:

Fig.1 High Level Architecture

The application architecture consists of a few components.

- Client application: the client application is a smart phone app that has the brain to collect data from other health apps, sensors on the phone, and process the data and also interacts with the user collecting meaningful information as well as alerting the user.
- Local Datastore: The app also has a local data store where the historical as well as current data is stored for further analysis and processing; this data is stored in an encrypted format using a certificate to ensure anyone from tampering with the data.

User Experience

Below are the various screens of the app.

- Home Screen: This screen has four buttons. 1. Alerts 2. Reports 3. Learn and 4. Log.
- Alerts Screen: This screen shows any alerts that the app has for the user.
- Reports Screen: This screen shows detailed reports of historical data for the user. Example: it shows how the user weight trend has been over months.
- Learn Screen: This screen shows links to educate the user to take control of her health. Example: shows videos that will help take steps to lose weight.
- Log Data Screen: This screen allows the user to log data on a periodic basis for the app to consume.

The following screenshots show the user experience of the various screens.

Home Screen
Reports

Alerts

Learn

Log

A. Technology:

The app can be implemented on a iPhone using technologies like iOS, Xcode, SwiftUI and UIKit. Airtable can be used as a technology for storing data. Similar equivalent technologies exist on Andriod phones – you can build the app using java and use SQLite kind of technology for storing data on the phone.

S.No.	User had PCOS	Acne	Weight	Periods	Hair	Number of Symptoms	1 symptom and PCOS	1 symptom no PCOS	2 symptom PCOS	2 symptom no PCOS
1	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
2	No		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
3	No			X	X	2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
4	No		X			1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
5	Yes			X		1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
6	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
7	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
8	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
9	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
10	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
11	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
12	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
13	No				X	1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
14	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
15	No				X	1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
16	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
17	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
18	No		X			1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
19	No				X	1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
20	Yes			X		1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
21	Yes			X		1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
22	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
23	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
24	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
25	Yes		X	X	X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
26	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
27	No	X	X	X	X	4	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
28	No	X		X	X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
29	No		X	X	X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
30	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
31	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
32	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
33	Yes			X		1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
34	Yes		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
35	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
36	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
37	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
38	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
39	Yes			X	X	2	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
40	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
41	No		X			1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
42	No	X			X	2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
43	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
44	No	X	X	X		3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
45	Yes		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
46	Yes			X		1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
47	Yes	X	X	X	X	4	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
48	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
49	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
50	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
51	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
52	Yes		X	X	X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
53	No				X	1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
54	Yes			X		1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE

55	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
56	Yes		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
57	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
58	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
59	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
60	Yes					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
61	Yes	X		X		2	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
62	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
63	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
64	Yes					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
65	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
66	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
67	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
68	Yes	X		X	X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
69	Yes		X	X	X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
70	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
71	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
72	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
73	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
74	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
75	No	X	X	X		3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
76	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
77	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
78	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
79	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
80	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
81	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
82	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
83	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
84	No	X		X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
85	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
86	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
87	No	X			X	2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
88	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
89	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
90	No		X			1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
91	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
92	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
93	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
94	Yes				X	1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
95	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
96	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
97	Yes					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
98	No		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
99	No	X			X	2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
100	Yes					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
101	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
102	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
103	No				X	1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
104	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
105	Yes			X		1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
106	No		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
107	Yes			X		1	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
108	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE

109	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
110	No	X	X	X	X	4	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
111	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
112	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
113	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
114	Yes	X	X		X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
115	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
116	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
117	No		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
118	Yes		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
119	No	X			X	2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
120	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
121	No			X	X	2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
122	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
123	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
124	No	X		X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
125	No	X		X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
126	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
127	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
128	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
129	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
130	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
131	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
132	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
133	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
134	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
135	Yes		X	X	X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
136	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
137	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
138	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
139	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
140	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
141	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
142	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
143	No		X			1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
144	No		X			1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
145	No		X			1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
146	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
147	No		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
148	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
149	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
150	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
151	No	X		X	X	3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
152	Yes	X	X	X	X	4	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
153	No	X	X			2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
154	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
155	No	X		X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
156	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
157	Yes		X	X		2	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE
158	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
159	No			X	X	2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
160	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
161	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
162	No		X			1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE

163	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
164	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
165	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
166	Yes	X	X	X		3	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
167	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
168	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
169	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
170	No	X	X	X	X	4	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
171	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
172	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
173	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
174	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
175	No	X	X			2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
176	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
178	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
179	No	X			X	2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
180	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
181	No	X		X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
182	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
183	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
184	No	X				1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
185	No	X	X	X	X	4	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
186	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
187	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
188	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
189	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
190	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
191	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
192	No					0	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE
193	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
194	No			X		1	FALSE	TRUE	FALSE	FALSE
195	No	X		X		2	FALSE	FALSE	FALSE	TRUE
196	29						25	82	16	30

# of people with 1+ symptom with PCOS	# of people with 1+ symptom without PCOS	# of people with 2+ symptoms with PCOS	# of people with 2+ symptoms without PCOS
23.36%		35%	
number of people with one symptom that actually had pcos		# of people with two symptoms that had PCOS	

B. Privacy

All of the user data is anonymized and encrypted using a certificate that is generated at the time of installation. This cert is stored on the certificate store of the native OS which provides the security for the certificate itself. Once the cert is in place,

the app uses this to encrypt and decrypt data as it updates or retrieves the data. There is no need to store any data to identify the user other than a unique id that is generated at the time of installation.

VII. Conclusion and Future Scope

PCOS is a major problem plaguing women with dramatic downstream consequences. The lack of education and delayed nature of the diagnosis especially makes it hard to detect and act on. Having an early warning system to identify the contributing factors sooner will allow women to take charge of their health and help effectively address it at the roots. The mechanism presented in this paper based on literature and customer validation clearly proves a very effective system to notify the user months/years before the onset of PCOS allowing the patient/physician to act on them when the condition is trivial and prevent the patient from developing PCOS. The algorithm proves to be 86.2% effective in detecting and notifying the patterns sooner which helps the patients to take measures and easily recover, thereby dramatically reducing the number of people that develop PCOS. Smart phone technology allows us to be easily accessible and effective. This can be further extended to cover areas and conditions other than PCOS to help improve general health.

VIII. References

- [1] Cross-sectional Study on the Knowledge and Prevalence of PCOS at a Multiethnic University Rao, Manisha MS^a; Broughton, K. Shane PhD^o; LeMieux, Monique J. PhD^b *Progress in Preventive Medicine* ();p e0028, June 2020. | DOI: 10.1097/pp9.000000000000028

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- [3] A cross sectional study of PCOS amongst adolsence and young girls in mumbai, India <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4056129/>

IX. Appendix